

TOUGHNESS MODELLING OF SEMI-CRYSTALLINE POLYMER AND UNIDIRECTIONAL SEMI-CRYSTALLINE COMPOSITE.

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ABSTRACT

Polymer toughness is highly dependent of the polymer microstructure. When one describes the polymer morphology by the ratio of two values characterizing the polymer described (i.e. spherulite radius (R) and interspherulite distance (L)), the toughness graph reaches a maximum value which is related to a critical ratio. The results of the developed geometric model allow to propose a two double-effect mechanism : the radius effect which energetically favours trans-spherulitic crack pattern, and the boundary effect, which energetically favours the inter-spherulitic crack pattern. Composite toughness is highly function of the fibre volume fraction and the matrix morphology. A model is developed to calculate the contribution of the fibres and the matrix to the interlaminar toughness in mode I of unidirectional composites. The microstructure of the matrix in composites is so complex that it is to be considered as the results of the superposition of different microstructure units. The microstructure units are described by the ratio of two values characterizing the composite (i.e. fibre radius (r) and spherulite radius (R)). The model is applied to the case of glass reinforced poly-aryl-amide.

KEYWORDS : thermoplastic, composite, fracture toughness, crystallinity, modelling

1. INTRODUCTION

Compact tension tests carried out on poly-aryl-amide specimens show a relation between microstructure and properties⁽¹⁾. Specimens are crystallized using different techniques to provide different morphologies⁽¹⁾ where spherulites are not yet impinged and isolated in a continuous amorphous phase. The toughness results are reported in function as a the calculated degree of

Figure 1. Compact Tension results : the critical energy release rate, in mode I loading, G_{Ic} (initiation value) for poly-aryl-amide specimens with different degrees of crystallinity (X_r).

The graphs toughness reaches a maximum for a degree of crystallinity around 10%. From those experimental observations, the microstructural effects on polymer toughness are modelled to provide a better understanding of the mechanisms.

2. MODELLING ASSUMPTIONS

A geometrical model has been developed to predict the influence of the microstructure on the semi-crystalline polymer and the composite fracture toughness. It is based on an approach initiated by Saghizadeh and Dharan (2), and further developed by Ivens and al.(3) on thermoset composites.

2.1. Degree of crystallinity and fibre volume fraction

In the model, the different stages of crystallization are considered to provide a microstructure which should influence the fracture toughness. Polymers crystallized from the melt are known to be organized in spherulites (4, 5).

The degree of crystallinity (X_r) is defined as the product of two factors :

$$X_r = X_{r_s} \times v_s \tag{1}$$

where v_s is

$$v_s = \frac{\text{Volume} \cdot \text{spherulite}}{\text{Volume} \cdot \text{polymer} \cdot \text{cell}} \tag{2}$$

and X_{r_s} is the degree of crystallinity of the spherulite, assumed to be fixed at 50 % for the different microstructures.

The fibre volume fraction (vf) is defined as :

$$v_f = \frac{\text{Volume} \cdot \text{fibres}}{\text{Volume} \cdot \text{composite} \cdot \text{cell}} \quad (3)$$

2.2. Unit cell

In the model, a unit cell is defined (figure 2); it illustrates the morphology of semi-crystalline polymer during the crystallization process and contains one spherulite in a continuous amorphous phase for pure polymer; for composites the unit cell contains one fibre and three spherulites embedded in a continuous amorphous phase.

The following geometrical parameters are defined : R, the spherulite radius, r, the fibre radius and L the inter-spherulite distance.

Figure 2 : Schematic representation in two dimensions of the unit cell considered in the geometric modelling; a. Polymer; b. Composite.

2.3. Crack path

When a crack interacts with a fibre, and if it is assumed that the interface is the weak spot, the crack will grow at the interface. The phenomenon is illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the crack interaction with a fibre.

A crack can also be deviated by a spherulite and can grow at its boundary (figure 4); it is called an inter-spherulitic crack. The second crack path is trans-spherulitic, through the spherulite (figure 4). Along the crack path, mixed mode loading exists on a microscopy level. To the inter- and trans-spherulitic crack paths are associated a critical strain energy release rate which will be calculated in the model. Finally, the crack will follow the path of minimal crack growth energy.

Figure 4 : Schematic representation of inter- and trans-spherulitic crack path.

2.4. Material toughness

Because the interlaminar fracture toughness is defined by the energy needed to onset a crack, this mechanical property is studied by characterizing a crack growing in the material. The energy needed to allow a crack to grow is consumed by cracking the continuous amorphous phase, the spherulite (or the spherulite boundaries) and the fibre interface. The composite toughness is therefore calculated as the sum of the contribution of those three components.

$$\text{Area}_{\text{crack}} \times G_{\text{compo,c}} = f \times (\overline{F \times G_{f,c}}) + a \times (\overline{A \times G_{a,c}}) + i \times (\overline{S_i \times G_{s,i,c}}) + t \times (\overline{S_t \times G_{s,t,c}})$$

with f , i , t and a are respectively the probability for a crack to grow around the fibres, around a spherulite, through it or through the amorphous phase. F , A , S_i and S_t are respectively the crack area in the crossed zones; and $G_{f,c}$, $G_{a,c}$, $G_{i,c}$ and $G_{t,c}$ are critical energy release rate for the different considered zones. For pure polymer, f is equal to zero.

3. POLYMER MODELLING RESULTS

3.1. Polymer toughness equation

The contribution of the amorphous phase and of the spherulites to polymer fracture toughness is calculated in the model and is expressed as a function of the relative position of the angle α which separates pure mode I (point A, figure 4) and the contact point between the crack and the spherulite boundary. In reference (6), the formulas are derived, giving as results :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Area}_{\text{crack}} \times G_{\text{poly,I,c}} = G_{a,I,c} \times & \left[(L+2R)^2 - \frac{\pi R^3}{(L+2R)} \right] + \frac{2R(1-\cos\alpha_{\text{crit}})}{\alpha_{\text{crit}}(L+2R)} \times \\ & R^2 \left(5267\alpha_{\text{crit}} + 11974\alpha_{\text{crit}}^2 + 8141\alpha_{\text{crit}}^3 - 5643\alpha_{\text{crit}}^4 + 2155\alpha_{\text{crit}}^5 \right) \left[\frac{G_{i,I,c}}{G_{a,I,c}} \right]^3 + \\ & \frac{2R\cos\alpha_{\text{crit}}}{L+2R} \left[\frac{1}{\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha_{\text{crit}}} \right] \times R^2 \left(343.79 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha_{\text{crit}} \right) + 24351 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha_{\text{crit}} \right)^2 - 7233 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \alpha_{\text{crit}} \right)^3 \right) \left[\frac{G_{t,I,c}}{G_{a,I,c}} \right]^3 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Area}_{\text{crack}} = (L+2R)^2 \quad (6)$$

(n.b. a is expressed in rad and every term has the dimension of an energy in above relation).

A critical a is defined for which, when a is smaller than this value, only inter-spherulitic crack paths are energetically probable.

The equation (5) implies that the toughness is a function of the ratio R/L , the latter being directly function of the crystallinity degree, the toughness of the amorphous phase ($G_{a,I,c}$), and, finally, the toughness of the spherulite boundary ($G_{i,I,c}$) or the toughness of the spherulite ($G_{t,I,c}$). But, if the crystallinity degree can be experimentally measured, this is not the case for the three other factors. Taking into account the different crystallization models, the toughness of the spherulite boundary (i.e. $G_{i,I,c}$) must be constant for low spherulite radius or low R/L ratio. At a critical R/L ratio, $G_{i,I,c}$ decreases with the increase of R/L ratio. We take the assumption that $G_{i,I,c}/G_{t,I,c}$ decreases with $R/(L+2R)$ ratio following the equation :

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{for } \frac{R}{L+2R} > S \\ &\frac{G_{i,I,c}}{G_{t,I,c}} = C - B \times \left(\frac{\frac{R}{L+2R} - S}{A} \right)^2 \\ &\text{for } \frac{R}{L+2R} < S \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{G_{i,I,c}}{G_{t,I,c}} = C$$

with A, B, C and S constants.
 Moreover, $G_{t,I,c}$ is taken as a constant (D) multiplied by $G_{a,I,c}$.

3.2. Comparison with experimental data

In figure 5, the experimental results are compared to the modelling results for the parameters described above.

Figure 5. Comparison between experimental and modelling results.

The study of the effect (on polymer toughness) of the variables A, B, C, D and S and the comparison of theoretical results with experimental results lead to a few conclusions about spherulite toughness and boundary toughness.

If the model is accepted as such, a correlation between modelling and experimental results will be obtained when one assumes the following : $S=0.4$, $A=0.15$, $B=1.3$, $C=0.7$, $D=1.15$.

(S, A, B, C, and D being the parameters which appear in the equations (7)).

This means that, at the beginning of the crystallization process which is characterized by $R/(L+2R)$ ratio that is inferior to 0.4 and a crystallinity degree which is lower than 13.5 %, the $G_{i1c}:G_{t1c}:G_{a1c}$ ratio is comprised between 1:1.5:1 and 0.7:1:1. On the other hand, at the end of the crystallization process, the above ratio will be comprised between 0.15:1.5:1 and 0.1:1:1.

3.3. Conclusion

The toughness modelling provides the following interesting results :

First, it provides results in complete agreement with the experimental data. The toughness curve shows a maximum for a degree of crystallinity around 10 %.

Second, it provides a mechanism which explains the shape of the toughness curve. Two effects are observed, a radius effect, which means, that when spherulite radius increases, the trans-spherulitic crack path is energetically more favourable than inter-spherulitic crack one; and a boundary effect, which means that for large spherulites, when the radius increases, the inter-spherulitic crack path is energetically more favourable because segregation of impurities at the spherulite boundaries. The combination of the two effects and the lower value of the spherulite boundary toughness as compared to the spherulite body toughness leads to a toughness curve featuring a maximum.

Third, it provides values for the spherulite boundary and spherulite toughness. Those values are considered as material properties and could be later used to calculate toughness of material based on PAA. It is illustrated in the next chapter for PAA reinforced by glass fibres.

In literature (7,8,9), it is usually found that polymer toughness decreases with increasing the spherulite radius. This is concluded by comparison of specimens cooled from the melt at different rates. High cooling rates lead to small spherulites and low cooling rates lead to large spherulites. The cooling rate is usually taken as responsible for the decrease property. At low cooling rate, voids and impurities segregate at spherulite boundaries, however at high cooling rate, there is not enough time for significant segregation. As the cooling rate decreases, the crystallinity increases, and the mechanical properties are mainly dependent to the lamellar size and configuration. The modulus and strength usually increase (10,11,12), but the toughness decreases

This theory is only valid if the spherulite are impinged together and if small spherulites is the result of high cooling rates.

The observations which have been reported in this chapter are more general; segregation of impurities at spherulite boundaries can also occur if the spherulites are small, when there is enough time. But a more important parameter is the ratio R/L , which is directly function of the crystallinity degree. If one accepts this theory, specimens which crystallize from the melting state - at a temperature which is near the melting temperature - and for which sufficient time has passed to allow the overlapping of the spherulites, should have the same toughness as specimens which crystallize from the amorphous state - at a temperature which is near to the transition temperature - and for which sufficient time has passed to allow the overlapping of spherulites. This is true for crystallization at 150°C from the glass state and at 210°C from the melting state; in this case, the toughness amounts approximately to 5000 J/m². The microstructure is then characterized by an average spherulite radius around 9.25 mm ($s=1.65\text{mm}$) at 150°C and about 17.5 mm ($s=2.1\text{ mm}$) at 210°C (13).

4. COMPOSITE MODELLING RESULTS

The microstructure of a thermoplastic composite material is more complex than a pure polymer microstructural unit, but it can be the result of the superposition of different microstructure units described above; it is assumed that

$$M = m_1 \times M_1 + m_2 \times M_2 + \dots + m_i \times M_i$$

where M is the composite microstructure and M_i the different microstructural units possible; m_i are weighing factors.

According to this assumption, the composite toughness can be expressed as the sum of relative contribution of every microstructural unit.

Depending of the degree of crystallinity and fibre volume fraction, some of microstructural units are not possible (from geometrical considerations), but when microstructure units are well possible, it is assumed that each microstructural unit can be present in the composite material, with the same probability.

This theory is applied for GPAA composites, assuming that the four microstructural units, shown in figure 6, give a good representation of the real composite morphology. The mean toughness value is calculated for the composite material in function of the R/L ratio defined above (figure 7).

Figure 6 : Microstructural units formed found in a real composite. M0 is the microstructure of an amorphous composite; M1, M2, M3 and M4 are components of the microstructure of a crystalline composite.

Figure 7 : Calculated interlaminar fracture toughness as a function of R/(L+2R) ratio. The toughness of the composite characterized with the microstructure (M) is calculated as the average sum of the contribution of every microstructural unit (M1,M2,M3,M4).

The composite toughness decreases with $R/(L+2R)$ increasing. The crystalline composite microstructures characterized with $R/(L+2R)$ ratio lower than 0.5 could not be successfully produced, so no experimental data are available to compare with the modelling results. However, the modelling shows clearly that the composite toughness decreases with the degree of crystallinity increasing. Moreover, although, the pure polymer toughness is not a function of the spherulite radius, the composite toughness is well function of the spherulite radius. The composite microstructure is composed by different microstructure units. Some of them are only present for low spherulite radius or high spherulite radius. The model shows that spherulite contribution to composite toughness is function of the microstructural unit, which means that spherulite radius is an important parameter.

5. CONCLUSION

The composite toughness is drastically dependent to the microstructure. Composite microstructure is the result of the combination of different microstructure units. The influence of the crystallization parameters is different from one to another one. Depending of fibre radius, spherulite radius and nucleation density, composite microstructure is only composed by some of microstructure units. It results a complex dependence of the microstructure to the toughness. The different microstructure units can be observed after microscopic examination. Moreover, the spherulite growth can also be computer simulated (14).

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